

Positive identification of tungro virus disease by transmission tests in different locations in India.

Year	State	District	Locations where positive results were obtained ^a	Extent of disease
1971	Andhra Pradesh	West Godavari	Maruteru	Moderate
1972	Bihar	Sasaram	Sasaram	Mild
	West Bengal	Hooghli	Chinsurah	Mild
	Orissa	Cuttack	CRR I Farm	Mild
1973	Orissa	Cuttack	CRR I Farm, Imamnagar	Mild
		Sambalpur	Chiplima	Moderate
	West Bengal	Nadia	Ranaghat, Krishnagar, Habibpur	Severe
		Burdwan	Debipur, Bhatar Farm, Sarul, Pemra	Severe
		Hooghli	Chinsurah	Severe
	Tripura	West Tripura	Jangalia, Nalchar, Seasrimai, Vishalgarh, Gokulnagar	Severe
	Assam	Nowgong	Rangbeng	Moderate
Cacher		Gusaipur	Moderate	
Manipur	Central	Samanroll, Wanghal	Mild	
1974	Kerala	Allepey	Kuttanadu area	Moderate

^aCRR I = Central Rice Research Institute.

confirmed only through transmission tests. This method showed the occurrence of tungro earlier in the Indian states of West Bengal, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Karnataka, and Kerala. From 1971 to 1974, the authors collected suspected tungro samples from 30 locations in 8 Indian states and conducted transmission tests on them.

Tungro disease in general was found to be a problem in northeastern, eastern, and southern India (see table). For still unknown reasons, it occurs in epidemic form only in certain years. Epidemics

occurred in parts of northeastern and eastern India in 1969 and 1973, and in the Kuttanadu area of Kerala in 1974.

The two green leafhopper vectors of tungro, *Nephotettix virescens* and *N. nigropictus*, are found throughout India, and high populations are recorded in the states of Assam, Manipur, Tripura, West Bengal, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, and Andhra Pradesh. Although tungro is generally spread by *N. virescens*, it was associated with *N. nigropictus* in Kerala in 1974 and Manipur in 1973. ❧

Incidence of sheath rot on three rice varieties

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Severe incidence of sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae* was observed on three dwarf rice varieties – IR32, CR73-7, and Sona – at the Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, Andhra Pradesh, during the rabi season (Dec.–Apr.) of 1972–73. Oblong, chocolate-colored spots, some with light centers,

developed on the top leaf sheaths. Most of the leaf-sheath areas were dark brown because the spots had coalesced. The panicles of some diseased tillers emerged only partially. A white fungus growth consisting of hyphae, conidia, and conidiophores was observed on the inner surfaces of the infected sheaths.

The spots were from 4 to 18 mm long and from 2 to 7 mm wide (see table). In Sona, 31% of the tillers were infected; in IR22, 9%; and in CR73-7, 10%. Disease incidence at the station was insignificant in 1974 and 1975. ❧

Size of sheath rot spots and disease incidence in three rice varieties. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Variety	Size of sheath rot spot (mm)		Diseased hills (%)	Diseased tillers (%)
	Range	Av.		
IR22	4–16 × 3–6	9.6 × 4.2	77	9
CR73-7	5–17 × 2–6	9.6 × 4.3	80	10
Sona	6–18 × 2–7	9.3 × 4.3	97	31

Chemical seed treatment to control Udbatta disease of paddy

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Udbatta caused by *Ephelis oryzae* is an increasingly important disease of paddy that causes considerable yield loss in Karnataka state. The disease affects both high yielding and local varieties. Estimated losses have been from 246.91 to 493.82 kg/ha, depending on disease incidence and intensity. The disease is reportedly borne in the seed, and symptoms show at the time of flowering.

The control measure currently recommended — keeping the seeds at 52–54°C for 20 min before sowing — is difficult for farmers to follow. Hence an experiment was conducted on chemical control. The treatments were Benlate, Bavistin, and Vitavax at 400 mg/kg of seed; hot water at 54°C for 20 minutes; and a control. Chemical-treated seeds were kept in cloth bags for 12 hours before sowing. Three-week-old seedlings were transplanted at 1 seedling/hill and observed for disease incidence at panicle initiation and grain formation stages.

Three seasons' data indicated that Benlate, Bavistin, and hot water were all superior to the control, while Benlate and Bavistin controlled the disease as well as hot water. ❧

“Rice abortion” or sheath rot—a serious rice disease in Thailand

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“Rice abortion” is the name that Thai farmers have given to a widespread disorder of rice with characteristics similar to those of sheath rot disease. It was first reported in 1969 as a secondary factor associated with stem borers, and has become increasingly serious, especially in the major rice-growing area of central Thailand. In 1975 the disease completely destroyed about 500 ha in Chachoengsao province. In severe cases, more than 70% of the infected plants produced no panicles.